

SOCIAL MEDIA EDUCATION AMONG ENGINEERING RESEARCH SCHOLARS IN KERALA DURING COVID 19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic triggered widespread global lockdowns, compelling nations to rethink educational paradigms. The India government suspended conventional educational activities, thrusting the nation into a digital transformation of higher education. The study investigates the profound shift towards e-learning, an educational modality that marries traditional classroom instruction with contemporary technology, catalyzing a paradigm shift in higher education. Within this evolving landscape, the research delves into the perspectives and experiences of engineering research scholars in Kerala, a cohort navigating the challenging terrain of e-learning. The study explores the shift to e-learning, combining traditional teaching with technology, driven by MOOCs with government support. The study examines learning platforms such as Google meet, balancing familiarity with privacy and security concerns and evaluates time constraints in e-learning, how this affecting both students and educators. The study advocates a comprehensive approach to enhance online education quality, emphasizing the need for thorough planning and increased government involvement.

Key words: E learning, COVID 19, Research scholars, Social media education, Engineering research

Introduction

A virus first identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 swiftly evolved into the deadliest global pandemic, rapidly spreading across multiple countries, transcending continents. The profound societal impact led to widespread lockdowns in numerous nations, reinforcing the significance of the adage “stay at home, stay safe.” In response, the India government issued a comprehensive suspension of activities, encompassing schools, universities, and other educational institutions, with an indefinite duration. In this dynamic context, educational institutions assumed a pivotal role in adapting to the global upheaval, leveraging e-learning platforms to mitigate substantial disruptions in student learning. Concurrently, the lockdown fostered a deeper understanding of e-learning, e-business, e-trading, and related concepts, positively influencing higher education worldwide. The government and universities initiated several e-learning programs to sustain the normal functioning of higher education institutions across the nation. However, the existing digital divide in the country posed significant challenges in developing and implementing effective e-learning strategies. Consequently, various organizations undertook trials of educational apps and e-learning platforms offering access to live classrooms as a potential solution.

As the pandemic disrupted traditional classroom models and access to research facilities, engineering research scholars in Kerala confronted a sudden and profound shift in their academic journey. This transformation was necessitated by the imperative to maintain the continuity of learning and research in an era of social distancing and lockdown. Consequently, the scholars turned to social media, a digital universe of connectivity and resources, to bridge the educational gap and redefine their academic experiences.

The study seeks to unravel the multifaceted impact of social media on engineering research scholars in Kerala during COVID-19 pandemic. It examines how the scholars harnessed the power of social media platforms to adopt, collaborate and innovate in their pursuit of knowledge. Through comprehensive research and analysis, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the evolving landscape of education, technology, and academia in post-pandemic world.

E Learning

Presently, the query that needs to be answered is what exactly is this e-learning? It is a method of education that makes use of both traditional classroom instruction and modern technological aids. According to the definition, "e-learning" is "the use of information and communication technologies for the purpose of enabling access to online teaching and learning resources." In addition, one example of this kind of instrument that has been utilized for educational purposes is known as e-learning. And over the course of time, this has evolved into a critical component of the higher education system. Even in our own nation, the government is working toward the goal of enabling countries to participate in Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC). Where hundreds of universities, companies, and not-for-profit organizations have launched MOOC along with other e-learning platforms and MOOC also offered entirely free services. Swayam, Coursera, and Future Learn are the providers of this MOOC. It consists of studying over the internet and using computers. E-learning refers to the process of acquiring knowledge using electronic media such as the internet, videotapes, CD-ROMs, and satellite television. E-learning is often referred to by its various synonyms, such as computer-based training (CBT) and web-based training (WBT), among others. Therefore, we can say that web-based training is simply e-learning, which implies that we do not need to install any kind of software on computers. This is because e-learning is web-based training. For us to be able to view, listen to, and learn each lesson on desktop, we need to have an internet connection and a web browser.

Kerala Technological University

The APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University, which is also known as the Kerala Technological University, is now being controlled by the government of the state of Kerala at this moment. It was once known as the Kerala Technological University, but in 2015, the university made the decision to change its name. The educational institution was given the name Kerala Technological University when it first started accepting students on May 21, 2014, and it has kept that name ever since. This day also served as the official beginning of the establishment of the university. The primary goal of this organization is to take the role of a thought leader during the process of developing engineering planning and technology-related policies for the state. In addition to this, it places a large emphasis on regulating the academic standards of all schools that are affiliated with the university, as well as increasing the academic standards of graduate, postgraduate, and research courses in engineering science, technology, and management. This is done to ensure that students receive an education that is of the highest possible quality. This is done to guarantee that the education that the children are receiving is of the very best possible standard. This is done with the intention of presenting students with educational opportunities that are of the highest possible standard. Research, the training and education of future professionals and the advancement of technological advancement are the primary focuses of the organization's mission and activities. The institution is committed to achieving all three of these objectives.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the e- learning status of engineering research scholars in Kerala during lockdown
- To identify and analyze the specific e- learning applications and platforms employed by engineering scholars during Pandemic
- To understand the challenges and issues encountered by scholars in the pursuit of e- learning various issues faced by scholars
- To find out the Perceptions, Problems, and expectations of the scholars in their e- learning.

Methodology used

In this study, a quantitative research approach was employed. The primary data collection method involved distributing structured questionnaires to gather information from 90 engineering research scholars of Kerala Technological University (KTU) Kerala. 120 questionnaires were distributed among the research scholars and only 90 scholars were responded. The questionnaire was designed to collect data on various aspects related to e- learning during the pandemic demographics, awareness, and familiarity with different e- learning methods, platforms, and the e- learning experience of research scholars during pandemic.

Quantitative data obtained from the questionnaire were subjected to statistical analysis. Percentage were utilized to present and interpret the findings. This method allowed a comprehensive understanding of the responses and enabled the identification of trends and pattern within the dataset. The study is limited only in engineering research scholars under the Kerala Technological University. Kerala.

5. Data Analysis

Gender-Wise Distribution of the Respondents

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	41	46%
Female	49	54%
Total	90	100%

Table- 1. Research Scholars - Gender-wise analysis

According to Table 1, the proportion of male respondents to the total population was 46%, while the proportion of female respondents to the entire population was 54%. There is a representation from both sides that is somewhat near to being equal in the gender-wise distribution of Kerala's Technical research scholars.

2. PLATFORMS USED FOR E- LEARNING

Amid the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, e- learning platforms emerged as the lifeline for engineering research scholars. These platforms facilitated remote education, enabling scholars to continue their academic pursuits and research endeavors from the safety of their homes. This question aimed to identify which platform is preferable to research scholars.

SL No	Platforms	Number	percentage
1	Google Meet	54	60%
2	Google classroom	10	11%
3	Zoom	11	12%
4	WebEx	15	17%
Total		90	100%

Table: 2 Preferable e- learning platform of research scholars

According to Table 2, it is evident that the preferred choices of virtual communication and learning platforms among scholars are as follows. Google Meet as the most widely used platform, with a significant majority of 60% of scholars utilizing it for virtual meetings and learning. Google Classroom is employed by 11% of scholars, zoom video conferencing tool is preferred by 12% of scholars for their virtual learning. WebEx is also a notable choice, with 17% of scholars opting for this platform, indicating its prominence in virtual communication, and learning environment.

Figure- 1.

The Figure- 1 reflect a diverse landscape of virtual platforms, with google meet leading the way in terms of adoption among scholars. The varied preferences may be influenced by factors such as familiarity, institutional choices, and specific requirements for virtual engagement.

3.HOW TO SHARE FILES IN DIFFERENT WAYS

During the time of COVID-19 pandemic, engineering research scholars faced unprecedented disruptions to their traditional modes of communication and knowledge transactions. In this context, utilization of social media tools like e mail, WhatsApp, Facebook, and other messaging platforms became indispensable for file sharing among scholars.

Table 3

Sl no	Information Sharing Methods	Number of Scholars	Percentage
1	E mail	63	70%
2	WhatsApp	18	20%
3	Facebook	9	10%
4	Other methods	0	0%

Table- 3 File sharing platforms

Table- 3 shows that a significant majority of 70% of scholars prefer email as the primary mode of communication and file transactions with their institutions. WhatsApp emerged as another prominent platform, with 20% of scholars receiving information and communication through this messaging platform. Although less prevalent compared to email and WhatsApp, Facebook still plays a role in information transfer, with 10% of scholars utilizing it for this purpose.

Figure- 2

Figure 2 give a clear picture that the significance of email as the primary means of communication among engineering research scholars. Additionally, the presence of WhatsApp and Facebook, along with other mentioned methods, reflects the scholar's adaptability readiness to embrace multiple communication channels in a remote learning environment during the pandemic.

4. PROBLEMS FACED BY THE SCHOLARS

Research scholars faced unique set of challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic, which disrupted traditional system of learning and research. some of the prominent hurdles they confronted while transitioning to e- learning is examined here.

SL NO	Problems faced	Number of scholars	Percentage
1	Internet connectivity	39	43.33%
2	Restricted access to resources	10	11.1%
3	Technical Difficulties	11	12.2%
4	Audio and video issues	18	20.0%
5	Time management challenges	12	13.33%

Table-4 Problems faced in e- learning

Table- 4 presents a comprehensive overview of the primary challenges identified by the scholars that the most prevalent issue cited by scholars was related to internet connectivity. Nearly half of the respondents (43.33%) faced difficulties due to uneven or unreliable internet access, impacting their ability to engage effectively in online learning and research activities. A significant number of scholars (11.1%) faced restricted access to essential resources and 12.2% scholars reported technical difficulties. Audio/ video disruptions during virtual meetings and classes were a notable concern, affecting one-fifth (20%) of the scholars. 13.33% is reported time management is a constraint in e learning environment.

Figure – 3

Figure- 3 reveals a range of challenges faced by scholars in the realm of e-learning and research. These challenges encompass issues related to internet connectivity, resource access, technical difficulties, audio/ video disruptions, and time management. Addressing these challenges is crucial for ensuring a more effective and productive e-learning experience for scholars in the modern educational landscape.

5. BENEFITS OF E LEARNING

Sl no	Benefits	Number of scholars	Percentage
1	E-learning is compatible with your lifestyle	45	50%
2	comfort with technology	21	23.3%
3	E-learning enables you to learn more efficiently than traditional learning	11	12.2%
4	Level of comfort with this method of teaching learning	13	14.5%

Table 5

Table- 5 shows that half of the scholars (50%) reported e learning made their academic pursuits more compatible with their lifestyles. A considerable percentage of scholars (23.3%) expressed a higher level of comfort with technology through e- learning. A portion of scholars (12,2%) believed that e- learning offered greater efficiency compared to traditional methods. 14.5 % of scholars reported feeling more comfortable with the e- learning environment.

6.SATISFACTION

Assessing the satisfaction level of scholars in e- learning is essential to gauge the effectiveness of this educational mode. Scholars satisfaction can provide insights into the strength and weakness of the e- learning experience. Here are some key factors to consider when assessing scholar satisfaction in e- learning.

SL NO	Opinion	Number of scholars	percentage
1	Very satisfied	48	53.4%
2	satisfied	12	13.3%
3	Neutral	15	16.7%
4	Moderately satisfied	10	11.1%
5	Not satisfied	5	5.5%

Table 6: Satisfaction level of research scholars

According to the data presented in Table 6, it is evident that the satisfaction level of engineering research scholars regarding e learning vary significantly. A majority of engineering research scholars (53.4%), expressed a high level of satisfaction with e learning. A notable portion of research scholars (13.3%) reported being satisfied with e- learning. A sizeable percentage of respondents (16.7%) remained neutral in their assessment of e learning. 11.11% of research scholars fell into the category of being moderately satisfied. A smaller but still significant percentage (5.5%) of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with e learning.

Figure- 4

The Figure- 4, satisfaction level of research scholars shows a diverse spectrum of opinions among engineering research scholars when it comes to e-learning. This underline the importance of considering individual preferences and needs when implementing e- learning strategies for this academic community.

Results

1. Most research researchers (60%) used the Google Meet platform for electronic learning.
2. During their e-learning, the majority of scholars used Email and the Watts app to transfer files.
3. The majority of scholars encountered issues such as internet access and trouble navigating numerous provisions in the app while utilizing it.
4. The majority of users prefer e-learning since it is more convenient for their lifestyle.
5. The majority of academics are pleased with e-learning.

Conclusion

During the pandemic period, e-learning acquired its own personality and proved to be a godsend for scholars in higher education institutions all over the world. As a result, the goal of this study was to better understand Engineering Research Scholars in Kerala students' opinions of e-learning.

This was an attempt to investigate many aspects of e-learning. Google Meet is still the most often used online tool for students. Classes. However, hurdles to effective e-learning were identified as Internet connectivity, privacy issues, audio difficulties, and time limits.

As a result, to obtain better results, institutions may priorities improving the quality of online education. This report provides a comprehensive overview of academics' attitudes towards online classes. However, online implementation was a success. Incorporating learning materials into the curriculum needs a well-planned strategy as well as a more active role for government at all levels.

Incorporating learning resources into the curriculum necessitates a well-thought-out strategy and a more active approach from the government at all levels.

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